

IMPACT OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES IN THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN SAN NARCISO, QUEZON

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 5

Pages: 788-797

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2879

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14615306

Manuscript Accepted: 12-17-2024

Impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the Social Development of Senior High School Learners in San Narciso, Quezon

Christine Joy R. Iglip,* Maria Celerina D. Oreta, Melchor B. Espiritu
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aims to determine the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of senior high school learners in San Narciso, Quezon. The study involved 40 respondents from a private school located in San Narciso, Quezon. The researcher used questionnaire to gather reliable data answered by the target respondents. The descriptive method was used to gather data needed to determine the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of senior high school learners in San Narciso, Quezon. Nearly every one of them had age range of 16-17 years old (68%) and the rest falls in the age range of 18 years old and above (32%). Most of them are male (65%) while the remaining are female (35%). Respondents which are grade 11 and 12 have the same percentage of 20%. Upon the impact of cooperative learning strategies in their social development, the result shows that under Interpersonal Competence, students build interests with a mean of 4.15. Under Social Competence, students become motivated to participate with a mean of 4.1. While in Teamwork Competence, working in teams boost their morale and motivation which gained the highest rank with a mean of 4.23. Meanwhile, in problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies, the results show that in terms of group selection, decision-making takes more time got the highest mean of 4.2. Upon the roles of the group members, group mates' intimate relationships got the highest mean of 3.88. When it comes to evaluation, 3.83 stated that teacher's poor development of students' competence can influence students' motivation to learn. Thus, it indicates that there is a positive strong relationship between the perceived impact and problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies evidenced by Spearman Rho Coefficient of 0.476. This was to conclude that there is no significant relationship in the responses of various age groups, and the male and female responses. While, there is a significant relationship in the responses of grade 11 and 12 students on the impact of cooperative learning strategies in their social development.

Keywords: *cooperative learning strategies, evaluation, group selection, interpersonal competence, roles of group members, social competence*

Introduction

Cooperative Learning, sometimes called small-group learning, is an instructional strategy in which small groups of students work together on a common task. Cooperative learning happens when students work in small groups to achieve a common goal. Educators are able to use this method in every grade. Through open discussions, students are able to learn from each other. The task can be as simple as solving a multi-step math problem together, or as complex as developing a design for a new kind of school. In some cases, each group member is individually accountable for part of the task; in other cases, group members work together without formal role assignments Solomon (2024).

In the view of Solomon (2024), cooperative learning changes students' and teachers' roles in classrooms. The ownership of teaching and learning is shared by groups of students, and is no longer the sole responsibility of the teacher. The authority of setting goals, assessing learning, and facilitating learning is shared by all. Students have more opportunities to actively participate in their learning, question and challenge each other, share and discuss their ideas, and internalize their learning. Along with improving academic learning, cooperative learning helps students engage in thoughtful discourse and examine different perspectives, and it has been proven to increase students' self-esteem, motivation, and empathy.

When implemented well, cooperative learning encourages achievement, student discussion, active learning, student confidence, and motivation. The skills students develop while collaborating with others are different from the skills students develop while working independently. As more businesses organize employees into teams and task forces, the skills necessary to be a "team player" (e.g., verbalizing and justifying ideas, handling conflicts, collaborating, building consensus, and disagreeing politely) are becoming more valuable and useful. Using cooperative groups to accomplish academic tasks not only provide opportunities for students to develop interpersonal skills but also gives them authentic experiences that will help them be successful in their future careers.

To understand more what a cooperative learning is, it is a methodology that employs a variety of learning activities to improve students' understanding of a subject by using a structured approach which involves a series of steps, requiring students to create, analyze and apply concepts. Furthermore, it utilizes ideas of Vygotsky, Piaget, and Kohlberg in that both the individual and the social setting are active dynamics in the learning process as students attempt to imitate real-life learning Lombardi (2017).

The researcher chose to study the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of senior high school learners because nowadays it seems that people forgot the true essence of cooperative learning and there may be a possibility that placing students in small groups and telling them to work together does not guarantee that they will work cooperatively, so the researcher

expect them to know its impact upon developing their social aspect.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of senior high school learners in San Narciso, Quezon. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade?
2. What are the perceived impacts of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of the senior high school learners with respect to:
 - 2.1. interpersonal competence;
 - 2.2. social competence; and
 - 2.3. teamwork competence?
3. What are the problems encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies in terms of:
 - 3.1. group selection;
 - 3.2. roles of the group members; and
 - 3.3. evaluation?
4. Is there a significant relationship on the perceived impact and problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive survey method to collect data to measure the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of senior high school learners in San Narciso, Quezon. According to Creswell (2023), descriptive research method is a study that describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. The researcher used survey questionnaire as an instrument. Based on the survey's result the researcher was able to determine the details of the study.

Respondents

The study was conducted at St. Joseph's High School Inc. San Narciso, Quezon. The senior high school learners, Grade 11 and 12 were the respondents for this study.

The researcher randomly selected 40 students who are enrolled in St. Joseph's High School Inc. during the SY 2022-2023 and the impact of cooperative learning strategies in the social development of the learners was the focus of the study. The respondents were composed of 20 students from grade 11 and 20 students from grade 12 with a total of 40 student-respondents.

Instrument

The researcher used questionnaire. This questionnaire used a Likert scale of; 5 – Very Much Agree (VMA), 4 – Much Agree (MA), 3 – Moderately Agree (MoA), 2 – Less Agree (LA) and 1 – Least Agree (LeA). For understanding about the impact of cooperative learning strategies to selected grade 11 and grade 12 students of St. Joseph's High School, Inc. Part I of the questionnaire is composed of demographic profile of the respondents, and Part II included the Cooperative Learning Strategies and the problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies. The research instrument was validated by two experts. A pilot testing was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha to test the acceptability of the questionnaire. If the result is above 0.70, then there is an internal consistency in the questions/items. The result of the pilot testing is above 0.70 interpreted as acceptable.

Procedure

Target populations were grade 11 and grade 12 students of St. Joseph's High School, Inc. The descriptive research method using Likert scale was used to rate the impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the social development. Data were gathered through "simple random sampling" both male and female students of St. Joseph's High School, Inc. were selected to fill the questionnaire.

In administering the questionnaire, the researcher used the time allotted for vacant time to avoid distraction of class discussion. The student response was given enough time to answer the questions. After data gathering, the researcher collected them for tallying the scores and applied the statistical treatment used in the study.

Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter to the principal and adviser of grade 11 and grade 12 of the school. Upon approval, the researcher administered the instrument to the target respondents.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher used statistical measures to treat the collected data. All the data were carefully read and examined for

analysis. They were tallied and entered into a master list of the data collection sheet. Percentage and Frequency were used to interpret the profile of the respondents.

To get the weighted mean to describe the items in the indicators, the researcher used the formula (Calmorin, 2007; 116-118).

To test the correlation between the perceived impact and problems encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies, Spearman Rho was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data. All the data gathered were presented here in tabulated form with corresponding interpretation. The first part described the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and grade level. The second part is the impact of cooperative learning strategies with respect to: interpersonal competence, social competence, and teamwork competence. The third part is the problems encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies in terms of: group selection, roles of the group members, and evaluation. The fourth part includes the significant relationship of impact and problems encountered in Cooperative learning strategies.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
16-17 yrs old	27	68
18 yrs old and above	13	32
Total	40	100

Table 1 showed the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to age, where 27 or 68% were 16-17 years old and 13 or 32% were 18 years old and above which described that most of the respondents were 16-17 years old.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Silver et.al., (2023) which stated that decades of cross-national surveys have found that younger people tended to be more internationally oriented than older adults.

Based on the data in Table 1, the majority of respondents (68%) were 16-17 years old, while 32% were 18 and above. This indicated a higher representation of the younger age group in the survey. The findings suggested that the survey results predominantly reflected the perspectives and experiences of the 16-17-year-old demographic. This significant representation of younger respondents highlighted the importance of considering this age group's views in the study's conclusions.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	26	65
Female	14	35
Total	40	100

Table 2 revealed that in the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to sex, the majority of the respondents were male with 26 or 65%, rank 1 and the responses of the female composed of 14 or 35%, rank 2.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Pearson and West (1991) as cited by Leraas et al. (2018) which supports the hypothesis that masculine students will participate more in class than feminine students. Using the Personal Attributes Questionnaire to measure masculinity, they found that masculine students were more active participants in class than feminine students. Given that male students may be, but are not always, more masculine than female students, when researchers find sex differences in participation it might actually be due to psychological gender.

Upon interpreting these results, the higher proportion of male respondents was consistent with the findings of Pearson and West (1991), as cited by (Leraas et. al., 2018). Their research indicated that masculine students were more likely to participate actively in class compared to feminine students. The predominance of males in this sample reflected this trend, suggesting that male students may have been more engaged in class activities.

Table 3. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents According to Grade*

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
11	20	50
12	20	50
Total	40	100

Table 3 shows frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to grade where 50% are grade 11 and 50% are grade 12 which describes that both of the respondents are equal.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Aguillon et al. (2020) which stated that when groups were randomly called on by instructors, there was no difference in participation between men and women. Furthermore, (Ballen et al., 2019) showed equitable participation between men and women in smaller classes and when instructors used diverse teaching strategies.

Based on the data in Table 3, the equal distribution between Grade 11 and 12 respondents aligned with the findings of (Aguillon et al., 2020) and (Ballen et al., 2019), which highlighted that balanced participation could be observed across different groups. This equal representation supported the notion that there were no significant differences in participation based on grade level within the sample.

Table 4. Respondents' Assessment on the Impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the Social Development of Senior High School Learners in terms of Interpersonal Competence

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>Because of cooperative learning strategies, ...</i>		
1. we enjoyed sharing our thoughts and encouraged each other's opinion.	4.05	Much Agree
2. effective leadership, decision-making, trust-building, communication, and conflict management were provided.	4.40	Very Much Agree
3. students feel less pressure to succeed in an activity.	3.68	Much Agree
4. students build their interests.	4.15	Much Agree
5. learners are motivated to participate actively in the class activities.	4.1	Much Agree
Grand Mean	4.08	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

Table 4 shows the average mean distribution of the respondents on the impact of cooperative learning in the social development in terms of interpersonal competence, wherein most of the students answered that collaborative learning builds their interests with a mean of 4.15, which got the highest rank. Students feel less pressure to succeed in an activity got the lowest mean of 3.6. Overall, the respondents much agree that cooperative learning strategies build their interests as shown by the generated mean of 4.08.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Lynch (2016) which believes that the ideal classroom emphasizes curiosity and cooperation above all, and that the student's curiosity should determine what is taught.

The data from Table 4 clearly indicated that cooperative learning significantly enhanced students' interests and reduced their pressure to succeed, thus promoting a positive and supportive learning environment. These findings were consistent with existing studies, underscoring the importance of curiosity and collaboration in effective educational practices.

Table 5. Respondents' Assessment on the Impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the Social Development of Senior High School Learners in terms of Social Competence

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>Because of cooperative learning strategies...</i>		
1. social development can possibly think others as a role model.	3.98	Much Agree
2. we were able to keep a bond among us.	3.85	Much Agree
3. student becomes motivated to participate.	4.1	Much Agree
4. I had social interaction.	3.93	Much Agree
5. students feel much valued.	3.73	Much Agree
Grand Mean	3.92	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

Table 5 reveals the average mean distribution of the respondents on the impact of cooperative learning in the social development in terms of social competence. It revealed that students become motivated to participate got the highest mean of 4.1 and ranked first among the indicators. Conversely, they much agree that students feel much valued by the help of cooperative Learning Strategies with a mean of 3.73 and ranked last among the indicators. Overall, the respondents much agree that students become motivated to participate by the help of cooperative learning strategies evidenced by the generated mean of 3.92.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Carrier and Sales (1987) as cited by Abass (n.d.) found and observed that "students working cooperatively appeared to motivate each other to seek elective feedback to their responses and to practice items during learner control." Similarly, the study of (Johnson & Johnson, 2009) as cited by (Van & Roseth, 2019) stated that Cooperative learning has been known to increase students' learning motivation.

The results from Table 5 underscored the effectiveness of cooperative learning in motivating students and making them feel valued. These strategies not only increased participation but also fostered a supportive learning environment. The study's findings resonated with existing studies, reinforcing the positive impact of cooperative learning on student engagement and social development.

Table 6 shows the average mean distribution of the respondents on the impact of cooperative learning in the social development in terms of teamwork competence. The highest weighted mean score was for indicator number 5, it simply stated that respondents very much agree that working in teams boosts their morale and motivation with a mean of 4.23. The lowest mean was indicator 4 with a response of 3.25, lowest rank, wherein they moderately agree that they feel less pressured. Overall, the results showed that most respondents with an average mean of 3.93 much agreed that cooperative learning strategies boost their morale and motivation.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessment on the Impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the Social Development of Senior High School Learners in terms of Teamwork Competence

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>Because of cooperative learning strategies...</i>		
1. students learn how to listen to one another to function as a cohesive unit.	4.1	Much Agree
2. students learn how to listen to their leaders and coaches to perform their individual roles.	4.2	Much Agree
3. I had a strong working relationship.	3.85	Much Agree
4. I feel less stressed.	3.25	Moderately Agree
5. working in teams boosts students' morale and motivation.	4.23	Very Much Agree
Grand Mean	3.92	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Malan (2021) which stated that students in the cooperative learning class demonstrated higher scores on the motivational scale than students in the lecture class. She found that collaboration and interaction among students towards the shared goal of understanding and presenting the course material enhanced their motivation to complete the course work. Cooperative learning benefited students because they could exchange resources and information, and support and influence one another. Furthermore, interaction among students in the cooperative learning class resulted in improved self-confidence and reduced test anxiety compared to students in the lecture class.

Table 6 revealed that cooperative learning positively impacted students' teamwork competence by significantly boosting their morale and motivation. Despite some moderate agreement on reducing pressure, the overall perception was favorable. These findings were consistent with previous research, indicating that cooperative learning strategies are effective in creating a motivating and supportive educational environment.

Table 7. Respondents' Assessment on the Problems Encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies in terms of Group Selection

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Some individuals have dominating personalities.	3.85	Much Agree
2. Things get crowded and out of hand.	3.33	Moderately Agree
3. Segregation if individuals can occur.	3.45	Much Agree
4. Decision-making takes more time.	4.2	Much Agree
5. Someone may try to take over the group.	3.85	Much Agree
Grand Mean	3.74	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

Table 7 reveals the problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies in terms of group selection wherein indicator 4 has the highest mean of 4.2, stated that decision-making takes more time. Indicator 2 got a mean of 3.33, lowest rank which stated that things can get crowded and out of hand. Overall, it also revealed that the average mean of 3.74 indicates that respondents much agreed that the highest problem that can be encountered in cooperative learning strategies as per group selection was decision-making.

A study conducted by Healy et al. (2018) found similar results regarding the problems in cooperative learning strategies. The revealed that for educators who is not skilled in using cooperative learning, it might be time-consuming to set up as decisions have to be made about group size, group formation and how the group work will be assessed.

The data from Table 7 pointed out that the primary challenge in cooperative learning strategies related to group selection was the extensive time required for decision-making. While there were concerns about managing crowded groups, the primary issue was the time and effort needed to make effective group decisions. These findings are consistent with previous research, underscoring difficulties educators face in organizing and managing cooperative learning groups.

Table 8. Respondents' Assessment on the Problems Encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies with respect to the Roles of the Group Members

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Group mates' intimate relationship.	3.88	Much Agree
2. Unequal participation from students.	3.35	Moderately Agree
3. Pressure to compromise.	3.35	Moderately Agree
4. Lack of leadership.	3.43	Much Agree
5. No individual thinking.	2.83	Moderately Agree
Grand Mean	3.37	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

Table 8 reveals the problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies with respect to the roles of the group members. The respondents much agreed that group mates' intimate relationship ranks first as the highest problem when it comes to the roles of the group members evidenced by a mean of 3.88. On the other hand, they moderately agree that there is no individual thinking with a mean of 2.83 and ranked last among the indicators. However, the average mean of 3.37 revealed that the respondents moderately agree that group mates' intimate relationship is really a big problem upon giving roles.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Luo et al. (2021) which stated that some group members may engage in “social loafing.” When one or two people are assigned a task, they know they’re being watched and are apt to shoulder the burden. In a larger group, however, any given member will feel less personally responsible for what takes place in it. If too many members follow the natural tendency to observe rather than act, a group may lose its efficiency and thereby find it much more difficult to reach its aims.

Table 8 pointed out that while both issues impact group dynamics, the presence of intimate relationships among group members is identified as a more pressing problem compared to the lack of individual thinking. Addressing the complications arising from personal relationships could be crucial for improving the effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies, in line with findings from previous studies.

Table 9. Respondents' Assessment on the Problems Encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies in terms of Evaluation

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Teacher evaluating students may show bias to certain students, which may happen intentionally, or unintentionally.	3.58	Much Agree
2. Students usually receive the same grade, which is not fair to the people in the group who did all the work.	3.33	Moderately Agree
3. Because of cooperative learning, no real knowledge and understanding have been gained.	3.03	Moderately Agree
4. Teachers poor development of students' competence can influence students' motivation to learn.	3.83	Much Agree
5. Students are forced to hurry up their learning.	3.33	Moderately Agree
Grand Mean	3.42	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

Table 9 revealed the average mean distribution of the respondents on the problems encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies in terms of Evaluation wherein 3.83 stated that teacher’s poor development of students' competence can influence students' motivation to learn. Indicator 3 got a mean of 3.03, lowest rank, which stated that because of cooperative learning, no real knowledge and understanding have been gained.

The mentioned statement conforms with the findings of Thomas (2022) which stated that the teacher shortages can significantly depress student achievement, as schools often cancel courses due to vacancies or staff classes with substitutes and underprepared teachers who are not certified to teach their subject matter. Underprepared teachers leave their schools at 2 to 3 times the rate of those who enter with comprehensive preparation. High turnover rates, in turn, can contribute to staff instability that disrupts relationships with students and other teachers, undermines professional learning, and impedes collaboration, all of which are critical to creating the supportive environments students need after nearly two years of disrupted learning.

The problems identified in Table 9 highlighted the critical role of teacher competence in the success of cooperative learning strategies. The alignment with previous studies underscored the need for improved teacher preparation and support to address the challenges observed in cooperative learning contexts. Addressing these issues was essential for ensuring that cooperative learning achieved its intended goals of enhancing student understanding and engagement.

Table 10. Summary Table on the perceived impact of Cooperative Learning Strategies in the social development of Senior High School Learners

<i>Impact Of Cooperative Learning Strategies</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Interpersonal Competence	4.08	Much Agree
Social Competence	3.92	Much Agree
Teamwork Competence	3.93	Much Agree
Group Selection	3.74	Much Agree
Roles of the Group Members	3.37	Moderately Agree
Evaluation	3.42	Much Agree
Grand Mean	3.74	Much Agree

Legend: Least Agree (1.0-1.80), Less Agree (1.81-2.60), Moderately Agree (2.61-3.40), Agree (3.41-4.20), Very Much Agree (4.21-5.0)

The summary table displays the average mean and verbal interpretation of the impacts of Cooperative Learning Strategies. It indicates that the respondents much agreed that the interpersonal competence has the most significant impact among the indicators, with an average mean of 4.08. Conversely, the respondents moderately agreed that roles of the group members have the least impact on cooperative learning strategies, with a mean of 3.37. Overall, interpersonal competence, social competence, teamwork competence, group selection, roles of the group members, and evaluation have an impact on the Cooperative Learning Strategies, as demonstrated by the general mean of 3.74.

These findings support the study conducted by Han, S. L. & Son, H. S. (2020) which stated that interpersonal competence is often defined as a particular communication ability in interacting with others in a manner intended to achieve certain results or objectives (McConnell, 2018). It is usually related to teamwork or leadership and very often called forth in cooperative works or collaborative student learning. Thus, it is crucial in the process of human growth. Interpersonal competence is, therefore, an essential part of relationships with others and in social activities as well. Similarly, (Socratous, 2014) emphasizes the importance of interpersonal skills.

He quotes (Dewey, 1940), who argued that schools are responsible for the development of students' interests in many areas of learning. Dewey also proposes that all students should be encouraged to expand their horizons in an appropriate manner and to equip themselves with interpersonal/communication skills in multiple student group interactions.

The findings from Table 10 underscored the critical role of interpersonal competence in the effectiveness of cooperative learning strategies. The data aligned with previous research, which emphasized the importance of developing interpersonal skills for successful collaboration. This alignment highlighted the need to prioritize and enhance interpersonal competence to improve cooperative learning strategies.

Table 11. *Relationship between the Perceived Impact and Problems Encountered in Cooperative Learning Strategies*

Perceived Impact	Problems Encountered			
	Correlation Coefficient	Interpretation	p- value	Decision
	0.476	Strong Positive Correlation	0.002	Reject Ho

Legend: Spearman Correlation; ≥ 0.70 – Very strong relationship; 0.40 – 0.69 – Strong relationship; 0.30 – 0.39 – Moderate relationship; 0.20 – 0.29 – Weak relationship; 0.01 – 0.19 – No or negligible relationship

Table 11 indicates a positive strong relationship between the perceived impact and problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies as evidenced by Spearman Rho Coefficient of 0.476. Strong relationship suggests that as the perceived impact of cooperative learning strategies increases, the problems encountered in implementing those strategies also increase. Conversely, as the problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies increase, the perceived impact also increases.

The p value of 0.002 indicate that there is a significant relationship between the perceived impact and problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies.

The study conforms with the findings of Hung (2019) which stated that students gained group work skills, problem-solving skills, and confidence. However, they suffered challenges in report making and relationships. While some students reported benefits in communication, others revealed that it was challenging. The benefits or challenges were mainly the results of the participants' compliance with the principles of cooperative learning. It is implied from the study that teachers applying cooperative learning should play their key role as counsellor and supervisor to help students overcome problems arising from the tasks and socialization.

The data from Table 11 highlighted a significant and strong positive relationship between the perceived impact and problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies. This relationship, supported by previous research, underscored the need for effective teacher support to address the challenges faced while enhancing the benefits of cooperative learning.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions are derived:

Most of the respondents are 16-17 years old, male, and are both grade 11 and 12 students.

Senior high school learners in San Narciso, Quezon demonstrated a strong interest in building relationships under Interpersonal Competence. They also exhibited increased motivation to participate, reflecting improvements in Social Competence. The highest impact was observed in Teamwork Competence, where collaboration significantly enhanced students' morale and motivation, indicating that teamwork had the most significant effect on social development.

Senior high school learners encountered problems in cooperative learning. The most significant challenge is the time required for group selection which can greatly affect the whole group. This is followed by concerns related to interpersonal relationships among group mates. The least impactful issue, but still relevant, is the effectiveness of evaluation practices, particularly regarding the teacher's development of students' competence. Addressing these issues, starting with optimizing group selection and managing group dynamics, is crucial for improving cooperative learning outcomes.

There is a positive strong relationship between the impact and the problems encountered in cooperative learning strategies.

As a result of the study, the researcher would like to recommend the following:

To the School Administrators, they may conduct a specific approach so that it can greatly contribute in the development of the personal and social aspects of students when it comes to groupings, particularly in selecting a group mate.

To the Parents, they may help the school to encourage their children to practice equal treatment among other people and help them understand the true value or essence of cooperative learning.

To the Teachers, they may continue to give positive feedback and positive relationships which promotes a sense of school belonging in order to motivate the learners to join in a group and encourage them to participate cooperatively without being restricted by the fear of failure.

To the Students, they may look forward to continuing cooperation and consider the views of every member, seek for recommendations, and appreciate members contributions so that it can help improve decisions and produce expected results.

To the Future Researchers, they may conduct a parallel study using bigger population for more viable and reliable results. They may also use other variables not mentioned in the study.

References

- Abass, F. (n.d.). Cooperative Learning and Motivation. CORE. <https://core.ac.uk/reader/268140190>
- Abramczyk, A., & Jurkowski, S. (2020). Cooperative learning as an evidence-based teaching strategy: what teachers know, believe, and how they use it. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 46(3), 296–308. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1733402>
- Aguillon, S., Siegmund, G., Petipas, R., Drake, A., Cotner, S., & Ballen, C. (2020). Gender Differences in Student Participation in an Active-Learning Classroom. *CBE- Life Sciences Education*, 19(2). <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.19-03-0048>
- Agwu, U. D., & Nmadu, J. (2023). Students' interactive engagement, academic achievement and self-concept in chemistry: an evaluation of cooperative learning pedagogy. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 24(2), 688-705. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RP00148A>
- Akcay N. O. (2016). Implementation of cooperative learning model in preschool. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 5(3), 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v5n3p83>
- Aporbo, R. (2023). Impact of Cooperative Learning Strategy on Students' Academic Productivity. *Journal of Student and Education*, 1(1):16-26. <https://doi.org/10.54536/jse.v1i1.1506>
- Araban, S., Zainalipour, H., Saadi, R. H. R., Javdan, M., Sezide, K., & Sajjadi, S. (2012). Study of cooperative learning effects on self-efficacy and academic achievement in English lesson of high school students. *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, 2(9), 8524-8526. doi=f82f2382e7df07d8ee3289685c4fadd31085215a
- Ballen, C. J., Danielsen, M., Jorgensen, C., Grytnes, J. A., & Cortner, S. (2017). Norway's gender gap: Classroom participation in undergraduate introductory science. *Nordic Journal of STEM Education*, 1(1) 262-270. <https://doi.org/10.5324/njsteme.v1i1.2325>
- Blasco-Arcas, L., Buil, I., Hernández-Ortega, B., & Sese, F. J. (2013). Using clickers in class. The role of interactivity, active collaborative learning and engagement in learning performance. *Computers & Education*, 62, 102–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.10.019>
- Bridgeland, J., Bruce, M., & Hariharan, A. (2013). *The Missing Piece: A National Teacher Survey on How Social and Emotional Learning Can Empower Children and Transform Schools. A Report for CASEL.* Education Resource Information Center. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED558068>
- Cagatan, A. N. P., & Quirap, E. A. (2024). Collaborative learning and learners' academic performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 7(3), 1326-1335. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i03-57>
- Cooper, L. (2017, April n.d.). *Social emotional learning: The impacts of an implemented plan at a private Christian school in the urban setting (Master dissertation, Dordt College, Sioux Center, IA).* Dordt Digital Collections. https://digitalcollections.dordt.edu/med_theses/109/
- Creswell, J. W. (2023, n.d.). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches.* SAGE Publication Inc. https://www.ucg.ac.me/skladiste/blog_609332/objava_105202/fajlovi/Creswell.pdf
- Eslamian, D., Aref, K., & Aref, K. (2012). The Influence of Cooperative learning on Academic Performance. *Journal of Science*, 8(2), 200-203. https://doi.org/am0802/031_7593am0802_200_203
- Ghufron M. A., & Ermawati S. (2018). The strengths and weaknesses of cooperative learning and problem-based learning in EFL writing class: Teachers' and students' perspectives. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 657–672. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2018.11441a>
- Gonzales, W. D. W. & Torres, P. L. (2016). Filipino ESL Learners' Attitudes Toward Cooperative Learning and their Relationship to Reading Comprehension. *TESOL International Journal*, 11(2), 70-90.
- Han, S. L. & Son, H. S. (2020). Effects on cooperative learning on the improvement of interpersonal competence among students in classroom environments. *International Online Journal of Education and Teaching (IOJET)*, 7(1). 17-28. <http://iojet.org/index.php/IOJET/article/view/717>
- Healy, M., Doran, J., & McCutcheon, J. (2018). Cooperative Learning outcomes from cumulative experiences of group work: differences in student perceptions. *ResearchGate*, 27(3):1-23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639284.2018.1476893>
- Hung, B. P. (2019). Impacts of cooperative learning: A qualitative study with EFL students and teachers in Vietnamese colleges. *Issues in Educational Research*, 29(4), 1223-1240. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier29/hung.pdf>

- Jolliffe, W. (2015). Learning to learn together: cooperation, theory and practice. *ResearchGate*, 43(1), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279.2015.992617>
- Kuo, Y.-C., Walker, A. E., Schroder, K. E. E., & Belland, B. R. (2014). Interaction, internet self-efficacy, and self-regulated learning as predictors of student satisfaction in online education courses. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 20, 35–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2013.10.001>
- Leraas, B., Kippen, N., & Larson, S. (2018). Gender and Student Participation. *Education Resource Information Center*, 18(4): 51-70. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1200685>
- Lombardi, P. (2017, n.d.). Instructional Methods, Strategies, and Technologies to meet the Needs of all Learners [Master's thesis, Granite State College: School of Education]. University of Regina Pressbooks. <https://opentextbooks.uregina.ca/teachingdiverselearners/chapter/cooperative-learning-2/>
- Luo, Z., Marnburg, E., Ogaard, T., & Okumus, F. (2021). Exploring antecedents of social loafing in students' group work: A mixed-methods approach. *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2021.100314>
- Lynch, M. (2016, June 29). The Five attributes of successful schools. FMU Center of Excellence. <https://www.fmucenterofexcellence.org/bestpractice/lynch-m-2016-june-29-the-five-attributes-of-successful-schools/>
- Malan, M. (2021). The Effectiveness of Cooperative Learning in an Online Learning Environment through a Comparison of Group and Individual Marks. *Education Resource Information Center*, 19(6): 1-13. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1330706>
- Mendo-Lázaro, S., León-del-Barco, B., Felipe-Castaño, E., Polo-del-Río, M.-I., & Iglesias-Gallego, D. (2018). Cooperative Team Learning and the Development of Social Skills in Higher Education: The Variables Involved. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.01536>
- Namaziandost, E., Homayouni, M., & Rahmani, P. (2020). The impact of cooperative learning approach on the development of EFL learners' speaking fluency. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2020.1780811>
- Pangantihon, A.L., & Tantiado, R. (2024). Cooperative learning Strategies and Students' Well-being. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*, 7(6), 2732-2745. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijmra/v7-i06-41>
- Panggaga, S. (2021). Cooperative learning Strategy: Its Effects on Enhancing the vocabulary and Reading comprehension Skills of MSU-ILS Grade Six Pupils. *International Journal of Linguistics, and Literature and Translation*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.32996/ijllt.2021.4.4.7>
- Quines, Z. (2023). Developing Linguistic Competence and Critical Thinking Skills Through Cooperative Learning: An Assessment. *British Journal of Education*, 11(2):13-28. <https://doi.org/10.37745/rg.2013/vol11n21328>
- Silver, L., Fagan, M., Lippert, J., Greenwood, S., Baronavski, C., & Keegan, M. (2023, March 8). How Young Adults Wants Their Country to Engage with the World. Pew Research Center. <https://www.pewresearch.org/global/2023/03/08/how-young-adults-want-their-country-to-engage-with-the-world/>
- Solomon, S. (2024, April 3). Cooperative Learning: A Complete Guide for Teachers. TeacherVision. <https://www.teachervision.com/professional-development/cooperative-learning>
- Strebe, D. D. (2018). An efficient technique for creating a continuum of equal-area map projections. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, 45(6), 529-538. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15230406.2017.1405285>
- Tacadena, J., Pejoto, M., Garado, A., & Garcia, R.M. (2022). Blended learning environment and learners' attitude in cooperative learning. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 11(6), 105-111. <https://doi.org/10.586/ijrse.2022.187>
- Thomas, D. (2022, February 9). Teacher Shortages Take Center Stage. Learning Policy Institute. <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/blog/teacher-shortages-take-center-stage>
- Van Ryzin, M. J., & Roseth, C. J. (2019). Effects of cooperative learning on peer relations, empathy, and bullying in middle school. *Aggressive behavior*, 45(6), 643–651. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.21858>
- Vuopala, E., Hyvönen, P., & Järvelä, S. (2016). Interaction forms in successful collaborative learning in virtual learning environments. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 17(1), 25–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787415616730>
- Yusnani (2018). Theoretical Perspectives on Cooperative Learning in the 1st Annual International Conference on Language and Literature. *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(4), 976-986. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i4.2005>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Christine Joy R. Iglip

Eastern Quezon College, Inc. – Philippines

Maria Celerina D. Oreta, Ed.D.

Eastern Quezon College, Inc. – Philippines

Melchor B. Espiritu, Ed.D.

Eastern Quezon College, Inc. – Philippines